

TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTER OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS WHEN DESIGNING PEDAGOGICAL OBJECTS.

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In the world, the goal of training engineers, the legal basis for the activities of subjects, the development of mechanisms for the interaction of subjects united in a cluster, the need for technologies for implementing the cluster approach has increased.

Modern traditions of the development of education in our country are closely connected with the creation of a multi-level system consisting of primary, secondary and higher education. As a result of the educational process, it is necessary to ensure a guaranteed level of professional competence of future engineers, and this is achieved through the design of a number of pedagogical objects:

1. curriculum;
2. the trajectory of the professional training of an engineer;
3. methodical system of education. [1].

The design of pedagogical objects gives the educational process manufacturability, allowing you to realize the goal. At the same time, special attention is paid to the educational program, which must fully comply with the state educational standard and provide the opportunity to train a specialist capable of making responsible decisions.

Achieving this goal is carried out with the help of the workspace of designing the trajectory of the professional training of an engineer. As a basis for designing the curriculum and educational trajectory, we recommended the cluster method, which includes qualitative approaches based on pedagogical diagnostic experience and modern theoretical pedagogical methodology. To achieve the effectiveness of the educational process, it is not enough to develop an educational program and a trajectory for the professional training of a specialist. It is necessary to equip the educational process with didactic and diagnostic-qualimetric means that make it not only effective, but also literally productive.

Project activities to create a methodological system of education are weakly based on those methodological foundations that combine natural-philosophical and diagnostic approaches. [2] Indeed, the selection of didactic means is

essentially the process of forming the totality of all possible teaching means. The development of diagnostic and qualimetric tools is based, first of all, on the technologies of standardization of high-quality questionnaires and didactic tests. These technologies are almost completely based on the expert-selective method of pedagogical diagnostics. So, the cluster approach allows:

Stages of designing a cluster approach

Nº	Design Components of a Cluster Approach	Design elements	Design content
1.	Content of educational elements	development of a curriculum consisting of peer review and selection of structural elements	
2.	Specialist	structural elements of the curriculum	form the working space of project activities in the educational space based on an expert assessment of the level of interactions, presenting it in the form of a matrix
		trajectory of professional training of the future engineer	designing the trajectory of professional development, analyzing the configuration of the workspace of project activities in terms of achieving the least significance of the principle of least impact and pedagogical impact
3.	Development of a methodological training system	selective selection of didactic materials for the educational process	
		into yourself	a) expert selection of criteria and indicators; b) granting the status of an expert to the respondents, i.e. defendants; v) development of qualitative questionnaires that received the consensus of the opinions of the

			expert group
		didactic tests	a) sorting of structural elements by experts; b) selection of test tasks of different levels of complexity; c) formation of a selected group to test the assertion

This analysis can also be performed based on the cluster method. In accordance with this principle, the size of the pedagogical action should be as small as possible [3]. According to the discreteness principle, the minimum size of the pedagogical action should be achieved at each elementary, simplest, smallest point of the learning process. If this principle is violated, when mastering only one structural element, it will not be possible to achieve a minimum pedagogical implementation.

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